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SELECTING THE APPROPRIATE ENSEMBLE OF REGRESSION TREES MODEL FOR FISH SHAPE ALIGNMENT

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Abstract: We test various Ensemble of Regression Trees (ERT) models for fish shape alignment. Fish shape is represented as a number of landmarks at various body parts. From the position of these landmarks malformations can be detected, species variation can be discriminated, fish dimension can be estimated, etc. The popular facial shape alignment method ERT has been adapted for fish shape with hardware acceleration. ERT models with 4 or 26 landmarks have been trained with photographs from 2 datasets with underwater fish photographs. The models differ in their ERT parameters (cascades and trees). The normalized errors from each model and their training errors are presented. The average normalized error for 26 landmarks, ranges between 0.36% (1500 trees/stage) and 0.76% (250 trees/stage and tree depth=6). This error ranges between 1.39% (40 splits) and 1.59% (default ERT model) when 4 landmarks are used. Worst error is achieved when 4 landmarks are used although training was performed in a controlled environment with minimal variations in the background. This is due to the fact that the landmarks at the caudal fin and the upper and lower parts of the body cannot be accurately annotated. Thus, 3 of the 4 landmarks could not be placed accurately during the annotation of the training photographs

Keywords: Ensemble of Regression Trees, shape alignment, morphological feature extraction, hardware acceleration

1. INTRODUCTION

Fish farming faces various economic and environmental challenges owed to disease outbreaks and inefficient feeding methodologies. Fish tracking can reveal the behavior of the fish and detect if it is hungry to adjust the food quantity. On the other hand, the estimation of the fish mass through shape alignment can also improve the feeding process. Selecting the optimal harvest time based on the estimation of the fish mass can also reduce the feeding cost by selecting the time when the majority of the fish have reached the desired weight. In this paper, we explore the speed and accuracy that can be achieved with various ERT fish shape alignment models as well as their suitability for hardware acceleration.

Shape alignment is a helpful process for the morphological feature extraction. The extracted features can be used for identification, classification, and the measurement of fish dimensions. In [1], contour-based segmentation combined with missing shape recovery methods are presented. This technique addresses occlusion challenges in underwater fish images. The segmentation is refined and missing shapes are recovered by aligning the initial segmentation with representative contours. Geometric morphometric analysis has been employed in [2] to describe body morphological changes and growth trajectories. Insights into how shape variations impact fish behavior are presented. The approach presented in [3] addresses different fish shapes and poses in underwater video. In this way, feature discrimination and recognition accuracy are improved. Ground truth data in 3D are essential for accurate fish shape alignment. Accurate measurement of fish body length is important in aquaculture management.

In [4], stereo cameras with active laser scanning are employed to address water turbidity and fish movement. Passive stereo matching and active laser scanning is combined and the system achieves a mean absolute error of 1.15 mm for fish length ranging between 15 and 40 cm. This error corresponds to 98.7% agreement with manual measurements. The reported processing speed is 8-12 specimens per minute using Intel i7-6700 and NVIDIA GTX 1080 graphics card. Stereo vision is also used in [5] that integrates deep learning with stereo imaging. Dual Intel RealSense D455 cameras (1280×720 @ 30 fps) are used in conjunction with NVIDIA Jetson AGX Xavier. A

YOLOv7 model is trained on 15,000 annotated images displaying five fish species. The Mean Average Error (MAE) achieved is 0.89 mm (1.2% relative error). The processing speed is 22 fish/minute with 96.8% detection accuracy.

The approaches presented in [4] and [5] offer high accuracy but they need large datasets with high quality photographs for their training. The work presented in this paper concerns the morphological feature extraction of small fish belonging to mediterranean Sparidae species. Several ERT models are trained with relatively small datasets ranging between 500 and 1000 images. Large ERT models with larger convergence time do not necessarily achieve higher accuracy. A tradeoff has to be made between accuracy and speed in order to select the appropriate ERT model. Some of these ERT models can be implemented in hardware (with Field Programmable Gate Arrays – FPGAs) achieving high speed processing of real time videos. Some ERT models that demonstrate higher accuracy and shorter convergence time may need excessive hardware resources that cannot be offered by ordinary FPGAs.

The aim of this paper is to: (a) compare alternative ERT models that have been trained in terms of speed and accuracy, (b) present high accuracy (with a relative MAE<2%) ERT models that achieve this good accuracy even when they have been trained with a small dataset containing low resolution images, (c) provide additional statistical features for each one of the ERT models trained, such as normalized standard deviation and median error, (d) investigate which model can be implemented with hardware acceleration.

This paper is organized as follows. The framework of the system where the trained ERT models will be incorporated will be presented in Section 2. An introduction to ERT is summarized in Section 3. An overview of the trained ERT models and datasets used is presented in Section 4. The experimental results concerning the accuracy, speed and availability for hardware acceleration are discussed in Section 5. Finally, the conclusions of this work are presented in Section 6.

Figure 1. Block architecture of the smartFish system

2. System Framework Overview

The fish shape alignment performed by the ERT models that are presented in this paper is a process integrated in a larger smart aquaculture system (called smartFish). The block architecture of the smartFish system is shown in Fig. 1. The monitored fish are in the pool. A pair of cameras placed at specific distance between them are monitoring the fish swimming in the aquarium. The pair of cameras provide stereo vision that is necessary for the depth measurement, needed for the estimation of absolute fish dimensions. The pair of cameras is connected to a Desktop PC supported by a GPU for high processing speed. More specifically, a high-performance Asus RTX4060Ti GPU is used. The desktop runs Windows operating system, and software tools are developed for the following functions:

- fish object detection has been performed during training or in real time using KWEA [6], YOLO, Ultralytics [7], darknet etc. The input camera frames are processed on the Desktop PC to detect fish. Input frames are segmented and patches showing a single fish are extracted.

- The orientation of the single fish appearing in each patch is classified.

- Stereoscopic analysis supported by the pair of cameras is also performed at the Desktop PC to estimate the distance of the fish from the cameras.

- Batch of fish patches along with their estimated distance from the camera and their corresponding orientation estimation are regularly sent to the laptop+FPGA workstation to perform shape alignment.

- The 3D coordinates of the detected fish are used for fish tracking performed on the Desktop PC. The fish trajectories are analyzed to recognize the fish behavior.

A laptop connected to an AMD-Xilinx FPGA development board is used to perform hardware accelerated shape alignment. The laptop runs a compatible Ubuntu operating system version such as 18.04.5. Xilinx Vitis 2020.1 is installed on this laptop in order to run the HLS tool used for the hardware acceleration. The Xilinx FPGA ZCU102 development board performs shape alignment with hardware acceleration and measures the fish relative and absolute dimensions.

A Customer Mobile Application has also been developed for use by a fish market consumer. It has been developed using Microsoft Xamarin cross compiler in order to be compatible with Android or iOS smart phones. The functionality of the Customer Mobile Application includes the following:

- Photographs of the market fish are captured potentially from a known distance.

- The captured photographs are sent to the FPGA development board through FTP.

- Shape alignment is performed on the FPGA board and species variation can be estimated from the distance of specific landmarks. Moreover, fish dimensions and weight can also be estimated if the distance of the fish from the smart phone camera is known. In future versions, additional information like freshness, may also be measured.

- The results are stored by the FPGA at a memory card directory. They can be retrieved from this directory by the Customer Mobile Application through FTP in order to display the results to the fish market consumer phone.

Fish can also be monitored on a conveyor belt exploiting the same communication model with the FPGA as the Customer Mobile Application. Fish are captured from a camera with a known distance from the conveyor belt. Single fish image patches are extracted and their orientation is estimated. The triplet (fish image patch, distance, orientation) is sent to the FPGA board where shape alignment is performed using an ERT model that matches the detected orientation of the fish.

Using the smartFish system, the fish farm personnel can monitor the following parameters through the information uploaded by the edge devices (Desktop+GPU and FPGA development board) to the cloud infrastructure: fish tracking details including 3D coordinates and estimated speed, direction, acceleration, deceleration that characterize the fish behavior. The fish behavior can reveal hunger, threat, fish health, etc. Feeding process, disease treatment and harvest time, can be adjusted based on this information and alerts can be generated to inform the aquaculture personnel. The weight and mass of the fish can be estimated by projection of its size (length, height). Relative and absolute size measurement can be estimated through shape alignment and stereoscopic vision. The optimal time for harvest can be scheduled based on a statistically large number of fish.

Shape malformations can also be detected through shape alignment in order to recognize species variations but also fish health.

The Customer Mobile Application can be used by a fish market consumer to get informed about the fish that are sold. The customer captures fish photographs that are uploaded through FTP to the FPGA development board where shape alignment is performed. The results and conclusions that can be reached from shape alignment include species variation recognition and optionally fish dimensions and weight estimation. In future versions of the Customer Mobile Application, shape malformations can be used to extract information about the fish health. Moreover, fish freshness based on the color analysis of specific fish body parts will also be used.

3. Introduction to the Ensemble of Regression Trees Shape Alignment Method

The Ensemble of Regression Trees (ERT) method presented by Kazemi and Sullivan in [8] is a popular fast method initially proposed for facial shape alignment. It attempts to fit a shape (S) to an image (Img) which in our case displays a fish. The shape consists of L landmarks with coordinates $(x_{(i)}, y_{(i)})$, where $i=1,2,\dots, L$. These landmarks are chosen at specific points in the fish body like the nose, gills, and caudal fin. From the position and the distance between these landmarks species variation, identification and classification can be performed. The initial shape denoted as $S(0)$, is a mean shape derived from the training procedure.

$$S = [(x_i, y_i) | i = 1, 2, \dots, L] \quad (1)$$

The landmark positions are iteratively refined, at each step t , through a regression function R_t , which estimates the corrections needed. The update landmark position update is given by:

$$S^{t+1} = S^t + \Delta s_t, \quad t = 1, \dots, T \quad (2)$$

where Δs_t represents the correction applied at step t and is computed using an ensemble of N binary decision trees T_j :

$$\Delta s_t = R_t(Img, S_t) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N T_j(Img, S^t) \quad (3)$$

Each decision tree is trained to predict corrections for the landmark positions based on pixel intensity differences that lead to different paths in the tree from its root to its leaves. The binary split condition used is: $I = (p_1) - (p_2) \geq \theta$ where p_1 and p_2 are pixel gray level intensity values at specific locations in the image, and θ is a learned threshold.

The shape refinement process is iteratively applied, with each decision tree adjusting the shape estimate as follows:

$$S_{t+1} = S^t \sum_{j=1}^N T_j(Img, S^t) \quad (4)$$

All trees contribute equally to the final correction and this is a key feature for hardware acceleration because parallel processing paths can be defined where different sets of trees are traversed.

Table 1. ERT Models Trained with 26 Landmarks

Model name	Cascade Stages	Trees/Cascade	Tree Depth	HW impl. On ZCU102
<i>M26_0</i>	10	500	5	Yes
<i>M26_1</i>	12	500	5	Yes
<i>M26_2a</i>	10	1500	5	No
<i>M26_2b</i>	10	600	5	Yes
<i>M26_3</i>	10	500	7	No
<i>M26_4</i>	10	250	6	Yes

4. ERT Models Trained and Datasets Used

Two sets of ERT models have been trained based on different number of landmarks and datasets used. In the first set of models, 26 landmarks have been used as shown in Fig. 2. where the annotation of a photograph is shown using the tool Landmark Annotator that we have developed in order to create datasets compatible with the Deformable Shape Tracking (DEST) open source package [9] that we have customized for different operating systems (Ubuntu, Microsoft Visual Studio in Windows) and target platforms (AMD Xilinx Vitis and ZCU102 FPGA development board, please see [10] for more details). The ERT models trained with 26 landmarks appear in Table 1. The dataset UVIMEF [11] has been used. It contains underwater photographs of various Mediterranean fish species in open sea.

Figure 2. Annotating 26 landmarks in a photograph from the UVIMEF dataset.

The default ERT model is the *M26_0* where 10 cascade stages, each one containing 500 regression binary trees with depth equal to 5 ($2^5-1=31$ nodes) are used. In *M26_1* we investigate how much will the accuracy be increased if two additional cascade stages are used (the rest of the parameters are kept the same). In *M26_2* models we keep the default 10 cascade stages and tree depth, but increase the trees/cascade stage. More specifically, in *M26_2a*, 1500 trees per cascade stage are used while in *M26_2b*, 600 trees per cascade

stage are used. The reason we selected these two values is because if the trees / cascade stage are more than 600 trees, the model cannot be implemented with hardware acceleration because the FPGA of ZCU102 does not have enough resources. Model M26_3 uses trees with depth equal to 7 ($2^7-1=127$ nodes). This model cannot be implemented with hardware acceleration since the required hardware resources are four times higher than the default. Finally, we also investigate a model (M26_4) with equal hardware resource requirements with the default one, that has 250 trees/cascade stage and tree depth=6. It has to be noted that even if a model cannot be executed with hardware acceleration is still can be implemented in software.

Table 2. ERT Models Trained with 4 Landmarks

Model name	Other parameters	Trees/ Cascade	Tree Depth	HW impl. On ZCU102
M4_0		500	5	Yes
M4_1		1000	5	Yes
M4_2		500	6	Yes
M4_3	Splits=40	500	5	Yes
M4_4		250	6	Yes

The second set of ERT models has only 4 landmarks (as shown in Fig. 3) and it can be used to estimate fish length and height. These dimensions can also be projected to fish weight and mass. The models of this set were trained with a dataset containing underwater photographs from a controlled environment (aquarium) that has been constructed in the context of the smartFish project. The ERT models trained with 4 landmarks are listed in Table 2.

Fig. 3. Annotating 4 landmarks in a photograph for ERT model training

Model M4_0 uses the default ERT parameters (10 cascade stages, 500 trees/cascade stage and tree depth=5). Model M4_1 has 1000 trees/cascade stage while M4_2 uses tree depth=6. In M4_3 we modified a different ERT parameters which is the number of splits. This number was increased from 20 to 40. Finally, model M4_4 requires similar resources

to the default M4_0 but with half trees and tree depth=6.

5. Experimental Results - Discussion

In this section we present both the training error of each cascade stage of an ERT model (estimated by the application `dest_train` of the DEST package) and the evaluated test error as estimated by the application `dest_evaluate` of the DEST package. For the evaluation of the models trained with 26 landmarks, 50 of the 500 photographs dataset (UVIMEF) have been used as the test set. In the case of the models trained with 4 landmarks, 50 of the 1000 photographs dataset have been used for test. The `dest_evaluate` DEST application compares the trained model results with the annotation provided in the test set that serves as ground truth. The test error was normalized by dividing it with the distance between the fish mouth and caudal fin landmarks.

Using the M26 ERT models Fig. 4 shows the training errors of the models M26_0, M26_1, M26_4. As can be seen from this figure, the training errors between M26_0 and M26_4 are almost identical so we do not expect a better accuracy from one of these two models. Model M26_4 has a very small improvement in the final accuracy compared to the other two (1.1% instead of 1.2%) thus, it is not worth adding two additional cascade stages since error floor is reached earlier. Since these three models show a similar training error, we use only the default M26_0 to compare the training errors from the rest of the M26 models in Fig. 5. As can be seen from this figure model M26_3 shows the best training error (0.3%) followed by M26_2a (0.4%). However, these models cannot be implemented in hardware (see Table I). M26_2b has a reduced error compared to the default M26_0 at the first cascade stages but ends up with a similar one (around 1%).

Figure 4. Similar training error shown by M26_0, M26_1 and M26_4.

Figure 5. Training error comparison for the M26 models.

Figure 6. Training error comparison for the M4 models.

The training error of the M4 models is shown in Fig. 6. As can be seen from this figure, the training errors between the ERT models are more distinct. The lowest error (0.4%) is shown by M4_1 (600 trees / cascade stage). The models that use either tree depth=6 or number of splits=40, lead to identical training error (0.5%) at the final cascade stage. The default model M4_0 shows a slightly better error (0.6%) than the M4_4 (0.7%).

The training errors presented above can be used to compare the expected real accuracy that can be achieved. Moreover, they can also be used to determine how many cascade stages are necessary since more cascade stages add only extra delay if error floor has been reached earlier. For example, it is expected that M4_1 would achieve a similar accuracy with a model trained with the same parameters and only 7 cascade stages since the training error (0.4%) is not improved after the 7th cascade stage.

Concerning the test sets used, as already mentioned the M26 models have been tested on 50 photographs from the UVIMEF dataset that display Mediterranean fish species from open sea (see Fig. 2). The M4 models have been tested on 50 photographs that display underwater photograph of sea bass and sea bream fish in an aquarium developed at University of Patras for the needs of the smartFish project that supported this work. The normalized average error for the compared M26 models is displayed in Fig. 7.

Figure 7. Test error comparison for the M26 models.

Figure 8. Test error comparison for the M4 models.

As can be seen from Fig. 7, the lowest error is achieved by the M26_2a model with 1500 trees / cascade stage (0.36%). The highest average normalized error is achieved by the default model M26_0 (0.76%). Comparing the M4 models, the lowest average error is achieved by M4_3 with 40 splits (1.39%). The highest average normalized error is shown by the default M4_0.

Next we compare the normalized standard deviation error. In Fig. 9 and Fig. 10, the standard deviation error shown by the M26 and M4 models are compared, respectively.

Figure 9. Standard deviation error comparison for the M26 models.

Figure 10. Standard deviation error comparison for the M4 models.

From Fig. 9, it can be seen that again the lowest standard deviation error is achieved by M26_2a and the highest by the default M26_0. Concerning the M4 models, although M4_3 showed the lowest average error it shows the highest standard deviation error. The lowest standard deviation error is shown by the default M4_0 error.

The final statistical error we present for the trained models is the normalized median error. Fig. 11, shows the median error of the M26 models and Fig. 12, the median error for the M4 models.

Figure 11. Normalized median error comparison for the M26 models.

Figure 12. Normalized median error comparison for the M4 models.

From Fig. 11, we get similar results o Fig. 7. Again M26_2a shows the lowest median error (0.29%) and the default M26_0, the worst (0.64%). Although M4_3 achieved the lowest average error among the M4 models, it shows a relatively high median error as shown in Fig. 12. The lowest median error is achieved by M4_2 (tree depth=6) while the highest is achieved from M4_1 (1000 trees/cascade stage).

From the presented experimental results, it is obvious that there isn't a model showing the best performance in all the statistical parameters checked. For example, although M26_3 showed better training error than M26_2a, its test average error is worse. Similarly, the M4_1 model showed the lower training error but M4_3 showed the lowest test error. The standard deviation error of the M26 models follows a similar pattern than their average error. However, the standard deviation error of the M4 models follows a different pattern than their average errors. The median errors generally follow the same pattern than the average errors.

Example shape alignment of 26 landmarks on the same photograph is shown in Fig. 13a for M26_3 model and M26_4 model in Fig. 13b.

Fig. 13. Example 26 landmark alignment of M26_3 (a) and M26_4 (b).

Similarly, Fig. 4 shows an example shape alignment of 4 landmarks with the model M4_1 that has 1000 trees/cascade stage (Fig. 4a) and M4_3 with 40 splits (Fig. 4b). The alignment results are almost identical in both cases.

Fig. 14. Example 4 landmark alignment of M4_1 (a) and M4_3 (b).

Concerning the latency of processing a single photograph for shape alignment, it depends on the platform used but on a ZCU102 less than 15ms were needed by the default M26_0 model. The processing time is almost proportional to the cascade stages, the trees/cascade stage (if they are processed sequentially) and the tree depth. For example, M26_1 (12 cascade stages) is expected to show 20% higher latency than M26_0 (10 cascade stages). Similarly, M4_2 (tree depth=6) is also expected to show 20% higher latency than M4_0 (tree depth=5). If special hardware acceleration techniques are used this proportionality may not hold. As described in [10], in each cascade stage we split the processing of the regression trees in two parallel paths. Thus, in M4_0 with 500 trees/stage, the hardware implementation with 2 paths is expected to have half latency than the implementation with 1 path. The model M4_1 with 1000 trees per cascade stage is expected to show double latency with M4_0. However, the M4_0 with two processing paths should have only $\frac{1}{4}$ of the latency of M4_1 with one path. In practice the latency does not show the exact proportionality as described above because there are significant overheads like the transfer of model parameters from the storage before the model can run. A drastic reduction in the latency can be achieved if fewer cascade stages are used. Training errors can be used as reference to find the cascade stage where error floor is reached. There is no reason to use additional cascade stages then, since not further reduction to the error will be accomplished.

6. Conclusion

A number of Ensemble of Regression Trees (ERT) models were trained for fish shape alignment and shapes represented as 4 or 26 landmarks. Using such fish shape representations, several morphological features can be extracted to estimate the dimensions, malformations and distinguish fish species. This kind of information can be used to control feeding in fish farms, select optimal harvest time, etc. The training error was presented from the various ERT models, that can be used to predict the real time behavior of a combination of ERT parameters (cascade stages, regression trees / stage, tree depth, number of splits) and decide the number of cascade stages that are necessary. The training error ranged from 0.3% to 1.1%. Then the test average error of the models was presented that characterizes the real time error that can be achieved ranging from 0.36% to 1.59%. Using the experimental results presented in this paper along with the latency estimations discussed, a trade off can be done between accuracy and speed according to the system requirements that have to be met.

Future work will focus on testing more ERT models and evaluate them with external methods in real time operating conditions. A more detailed latency estimation will be presented for each model when implemented on a specific platform with or without hardware acceleration.

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